

THE INPUTS ARE ON INSERTED SILICON NON-BALANCED PROCESSES

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Abstract. It is shown that it is possible to change the fundamental parameters of initial silicon samples by controlling the concentration of nanostructures of clusters of input atoms in the volume of silicon material, and on the basis of this, it is shown that there are opportunities to create new class of devices in nanoelectronics.

Key words: silicon, overcompensation, diffusion, nanocluster, introduction, sulfur, diffusion.

ВХОДЫ НА ВСТАВЛЕННЫЕ КРЕМНИЕВЫЕ НЕСИММЕТРИЧНЫЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ

Аннотация. Показано, что можно изменять фундаментальные параметры исходных образцов кремния, управляя концентрацией наноструктур кластеров входных атомов в объеме кремниевого материала, и на основе этого показано, что существуют возможности создания новый класс устройств в нанoeлектронике.

Ключевые слова: кремний, сверхкомпенсация, диффузия, нанокластер, внедрение, сера, диффузия.

Semiconductor materials and devices and structures made on their basis are used more and more widely, especially the achievements in radio electronics, medical energy and computer technology cannot be imagined without semiconductors.

At present, control and control structures in the communication system and many similar electronic devices are based on integrated microcircuits made of semiconductor material.

At the basis of these are the main properties of semiconductor materials, that is, they are very sensitive to external influences, the devices manufactured on their basis weight and size, service life, at the same time, they differ in their resistance to various external influences. In all educational systems, great importance is attached to the teaching of semiconductor physics, but we believe that teaching them on the basis of interdisciplinarity is a guarantee of the effectiveness of the lesson It is shown that it is possible to change the fundamental parameters of the initial silicon samples by controlling the concentration of the nanostructures of clusters of lead atoms in the volume of the silicon material.

This new quantum-scale structure allows obtaining nanoscale clusters in silicon material.
Key words: silicon, overcompensation, diffusion, nanocluster, introduction, sulfur, diffusion.

A number of scientific researches are being conducted to obtain new nanocluster supercompensated materials. As a result of scientific research conducted in the world on the development of electronic devices on the basis of new materials, scientific results aimed at controlling the electrophysical parameters of semiconductor materials were obtained. We can cite the scientific works of the authors on the technology of introducing various input atoms into the crystal lattice by high-temperature diffusion method, the transition of silicon with input atoms into

a ferromagnetic state at low temperatures, and the characteristics of compensated silicon-based structures.

In the world, research on compensated silicon and clusters based on them is being carried out in the following priority directions, including the development of diodes with improved parameters based on silicon with introduced atoms of rare earth elements, the development of processes for obtaining nanoscale structures in compensated silicon, the determination of electrophysical properties of supercompensated semiconductors and multifunctional devices based on them development of magnetic, temperature, pressure and photo sensors, identification and justification of quantum and nanoscale effects occurring in three-dimensional nanoclusters.

Today, in the world, attention is focused on determining the technological prerequisites for the emergence of non-equilibrium processes in supercompensated silicon, as well as the physical phenomena and effects of the structures created on the basis of the new material. On the basis of their functional capabilities, great importance is attached to the creation of a new class of electronic devices and sensors.

In this regard, it is one of the important tasks to carry out targeted scientific research, including the following scientific research: the necessary electrophysical parameters of the initial semiconductor material and the iron transition group and determination of the composition of isovalent input atoms, selection of alloying methods related to the nature of input atoms, creation of a new class of electronic devices and sensors based on new physical phenomena, effects and their functional capabilities in silicon material.

Based on the knowledge of the technological methods of forming clusters in silicon, the interaction of incoming atoms and the concentration of structures and complexes in the crystal lattice the rules of control were studied and analyzed. It was shown that the formation of volume clusters is formed due to the interaction of the input atoms with the silicon crystal lattice or residual input atoms. It has been revealed that the formation of volumetric nanoclusters can be controlled by knowing the favorable thermodynamic conditions for the interaction of intermolecular atoms.

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